

Sustainable chemo-enzymatic synthesis of glycerol carbonate (meth)acrylate from glycidol and carbon dioxide enabled by ionic liquids technologies

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A sustainable chemo-enzymatic process for producing both glycerol carbonate acrylate (GCA) and glycerol carbonate methacrylate (GCMA), as useful monomers for preparation of biodegradable plastic materials, has been carried out taking advantage of the ionic liquids (ILs) technologies. The process consisted on two consecutive catalytic steps, which can be carried out by either sequential or one-pot experimental approaches. The glycidyl (meth)acrylate was firstly synthesized by enzymatic transesterification from (meth)acrylate vinyl ester with glycidol in Sponge Like Ionic Liquids (SLILs) as the reaction medium (100% yield after 6 h at 60 °C). SLILs not only provided a suitable reaction medium but also allowed the simple isolation of the resulting glycidyl esters as an IL-free pure fraction through a cooling / centrifugation straightforward protocol. The second step consisted in the GCA, or GCMA, synthesis as the outcome of the cycloaddition of CO₂ to the obtained glycidyl acrylate or glycidyl methacrylate, respectively, catalysed by a covalently attached 1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium moiety (Supported Ionic Liquids-Like Phase, SILLP) in a solvent-free system and under mild conditions (60 °C, 1-10 bar), leading to up to 100 % yield after 6 h. The components of the reaction system (biocatalyst/SLIL/SILLP) can be fully recovered and reused for at least 6 cycles with unchanged catalytic performance.

Introduction

One of the main global challenges of this century is to reduce the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. This requires the development of technological solutions for CO₂ capture,¹ and its conversion into added-value products (*e.g.* formic acid,² methanol,³ etc.). A second important global challenge is the substitution of recalcitrant plastics (*e.g.* polyurethanes, PU, etc.),⁴ leading to serious ecological threats by their accumulation in the environment, for bio-based and biodegradable polymeric materials fulfilling circular economy criteria (*e.g.* water-based non-isocyanate polyurethane-ureas, etc.).⁵ Green chemistry can provide sustainable solutions for solving those global challenges, directly contributing to improve our quality of life.

Glycerol is a renewable chemical from biomass of great academic and industrial interest because of its large availability as a by-product in the manufacturing of biodiesel. Glycerol can be used as a raw

material in the synthesis of numerous products (*e.g.* polymers, solvents, fuel additives, etc.).⁶ Among its derivatives, glycerol carbonate (GC), resulting from the net incorporation of a carbon dioxide molecule to glycerol,⁷ is a versatile molecule. The presence of both a hydroxyl and a cyclic carbonate group enables its use as a monomer in polymer synthesis.⁸ Furthermore, GC can also be modified by introducing other reactive moieties (*e.g.* acrylate groups) to produce new functionalized monomers for polymer chemistry.⁹

In this context, glycerol carbonate acrylate (GCA) and glycerol carbonate methacrylate (GCMA) have been described as useful monomers for the synthesis of several polymeric materials of particular relevance in fields like surface coating. Some examples include: hydroxyurethane acrylate copolymers used as photocurable thermosets for 3-D printing;¹⁰ poly(alkyl glycidate carbonate)s, degradable pressure-sensitive adhesives;¹¹ bio-based non isocyanate polyurethanes (NIPUs) with a wide range of mechanical properties,¹² ultraviolet polymerized GCMA/GCA-based polymer electrolytes for lithium secondary batteries;¹³ etc. Because of the interest of PUs, the combination of diamines and GCMA or GCA to obtain bio-based NIPUs via aza-Michael or aminolysis reactions represents an environmentally friendly approach not requiring the use of phosgene or isocyanate.¹⁴

Both GCMA and GCA monomers are usually obtained by classical methods of chemical synthesis like the reaction of GC with acryloyl chloride,^{14a,15} the transesterification of GC with methyl methacrylate,¹⁶ or the cycloaddition of CO₂ to glycidyl

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methacrylate.¹⁰ Such processes take place in organic solvents and require several hours of reaction at high temperature

Figure 1. Chemo-enzymatic synthesis of GCA or GCMA (4) by means of two consecutive catalytic reactions. **Step 1.** Novozym 435-catalyses the synthesis of glycidyl (meth)acrylate (3) by transesterification of vinyl (meth)acrylate (1) with glycidol (2) in [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] SLIL as reaction medium, followed by the separation of (3) from the IL by cooling and centrifugation. **Step 2.** 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium-based SILLPs-catalysed the synthesis of GCMA/GCA (4) by the cycloaddition of CO₂ into the epoxide ring of (3). Vinyl acrylate (R = -H); vinyl methacrylate (R = -CH₃).

(80 - 100 °C), as well as further purification steps, being far from fulfilling Green Chemistry principles.¹⁷ The excellent selectivity of enzymes for chemical reactions is one of the most important tools in sustainable chemistry. Lipases are among the most important biocatalysts for the synthesis of valuable ester products through esterification or transesterification approaches in reaction media with a low water content.¹⁸ The reaction mechanism of serin-hydrolases, like lipases, occurs via a covalently linked acyl-enzyme intermediate, which deacylated through the nucleophilic attack of an alcohol leading to the corresponding ester product. In anhydrous reaction media, this process is enhanced by the use of activated acid acyl-donors, such as vinyl esters, because the vinyl alcohol released by the enzyme action tautomerizes to acetaldehyde, which cannot act again as a substrate for the enzyme, resulting in the full conversion of the acyl donor to the desired ester (see Fig. 1 A).¹⁹

The synthesis of GCMA, or GCA, by the lipase-catalysed transesterification of vinyl methacrylate or vinyl acrylate, respectively, with GC in organic solvents as reaction media (*i.e.* *t*-

butanol, 2-methyl-2-buthanol, etc.), has been also reported, achieving up to 95% yield after 24 h at 50 °C.²⁰ Alternatively, the synthesis of GCA was also reported through the cycloaddition of carbon dioxide to glycidyl methacrylate catalysed by immobilized bifunctional ammonium derivatives, with a 88% yield after 18 h at 10 bar CO₂ pressure and 90 °C.²¹

The greenness of chemical processes is strongly maintained by two main pillars, the selectivity of catalytic transformations, and the easy separation of pure products from reusable reaction media. Both the ionic liquid (ILs) technologies, and the exquisite catalytic efficiencies shown by enzymes in chemical transformations, are synergic tools with unique properties for developing integrated reaction and separation processes, able to directly provide pure products by straightforward and smart approaches.²² In this way, hydrophobic ILs based on cations with long alkyl side chains (*e.g.* 1-hexadecyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide, [C₁₆mim][NTf₂]) are temperature-switchable IL/solid phases that behave as sponge-like systems (Sponge-Like ILs, SLILs). A unique future of SLILs concerns their excellent suitability as reaction media for enzyme-catalysed chemical transformations, because of the exceptional level of activity and stability provided to biocatalysts,²³ (*e.g.* Novozym 435 shows up to 1370 days half life time in the SLIL octadecyltrimethylammonium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [C₁₈tma][NTf₂] at 60 °C).²⁴ Indeed, SLILs have been shown as exceptional reaction media for the biocatalytic synthesis of added-value products at temperatures higher than their melting point (*e.g.* biodiesel,²⁴ flavour acyl esters,²⁵ etc), enabling the easy separation of nearly pure products by using straightforward centrifugation/filtration approaches. The strong interactions established between the IL units and polar groups of amino acids of the outer shell of the protein facilitate the immobilization of the enzyme in the IL-phase.²³ Such IL-based reaction media have successfully been applied for developing two-step chemo-enzymatic transformations, showing an excellent suitability for multi-catalytic processes.²⁶ Furthermore, the covalent attachment of IL-like moieties onto solid supports (Supported Ionic Liquid-Like Phases, SILLPs),²⁷ represents a useful tool providing IL-based microenvironments suitable for continuous biocatalytic processes,²⁸ and with the potential to act as heterogeneous catalytic IL-phases.²⁹ This paper shows, by the first time, the synthesis of glycerol carbonate (meth)acrylate (GCMA or GCA) through a two-step catalytic approach based on the synergies between biocatalysis and the IL technologies (see Fig. 1). Initially, the enzymatic synthesis of glycidyl (meth)acrylate by transesterification of vinyl (meth)acrylate with glycidol was carried out in the [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] SLIL, with the ester product being easily separated by a simple cooling/centrifugation process. In a second step, the synthesis of GCA or GCMA was carried out by the cycloaddition of CO₂ to the epoxide ring of glycidyl (meth)acrylate in solvent-free media catalysed by SILLPs containing covalently attached 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium moieties. Alternatively, the direct immobilization of *Candida antarctica* lipase B (CALB) by adsorption onto 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium-based SILPs was successfully assayed in a one-pot combo system to simultaneously carry out the two catalytic steps leading to the solvent-free preparation of GCA or GCMA from glycidol and vinyl acrylate (or vinyl methacrylate) under CO₂ pressure. The excellent suitability of the proposed approaches was

demonstrated by the yield and purity of the obtained GCA (or GCMA), as well as by the recovery and further reuse of all the elements of the reaction system (biocatalyst, SILLPs, SLIL, etc.).

Figure 2. Synthesis of Supported Ionic Liquid-Like Phases (SILLPs).

Experimental

Materials

The commercial immobilized lipases (EC 3.1.1.3) Novozyme 435[®] (*Candida antarctica* Lipase B), Lypozyme TL IM[®] (*Thermomyces lanuginosus* Lipase), Lypozyme RM IM[®] (*Rhizomucor miehei* Lipase), and the non-immobilized CALB solution (Novozym 525L[®]) were from Novozymes S.A. (Spain). Vinyl acrylate (98% purity), vinyl methacrylate (98% purity), methyl acrylate (99% purity), methyl methacrylate (99% purity), glycidol (96% purity), molecular sieves 13x (MS13x; 270 mg H₂O per g adsorption capacity), Merrifield resins (HL and LL, 100-200 mesh), reagents, solvents and other chemicals were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich-Fluka (Spain). 1-Hexadecyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([C₁₆mim][NTf₂], 99% purity, mp 49 °C) was obtained from IoLiTec GmbH (Germany).

Preparation of Supported Ionic Liquid-Like Phases (SILLPs)

Polymeric supports containing covalently attached alkyl-imidazolium moieties were prepared by chemical modification of commercially available chloromethylated Merrifield-gel polymers (1.2 or 4.3 mEq. Cl/g polymer; 1% divinylbenzene, DVB) with the corresponding substituted imidazole (*i.e.* methylimidazole, butylimidazole or 1-decyl-2-methylimidazole). The resulting [Cl] anion-based SILLPs can be modified to the corresponding [NTf₂] SILLPs by anion metathesis in a further step (Fig. 2). As a representative example, the 1-methylimidazolium SILLP (SILLP-1, Table 2) was prepared as follows: In a round-bottomed flask, the Merrifield resin (5 g) was mixed with 20 mL of 1-methylimidazole (243.5 mmol) and the resulting suspension was stirred for 6 h at 80 °C. Afterwards, the suspension was filtered and the resulting solid polymer was consecutively washed with 20 mL of methanol, methanol:dichloromethane (1:1, v/v) and dichloromethane, being finally vacuum dried. The [NTf₂] anion-based SILLPs were obtained by anion metathesis, as follows: the corresponding [Cl]-based SILLP (5 g) was suspended in methanol (10 mL) and mixed with a 3 M [Li][NTf₂] aqueous solution (10 mL). The system was stirred for 24 h at RT, then filtered and washed with 20 mL of methanol, methanol:dichloromethane (1:1, v/v) and dichloromethane, and finally vacuum dried. The IL-like loading of each prepared support was calculated by elemental analysis. All these materials have been characterized by various techniques, such as FT-IR spectroscopy or Raman microspectroscopy, which confirmed the expected structures.³⁰

Immobilization of *Candida antarctica* Lipase B on SILLP

First, the commercial enzyme preparation was ultrafiltered, to eliminate all the low molecular weight additives, as follows: Novozym 525 L (25 mL) was diluted in water (225 mL), and the resulting solution was concentrated ten times by ultrafiltration at 6 °C by using a Vivaflow 50 (Sartorius) system equipped with polysulphone membranes (10 kDa cutoff). This process was repeated three times to obtain a 10.3 mg protein/mL CALB solution (CALB-SE), as determined by means of the Lowry method.³¹ Immobilised lipase derivatives were prepared by simply mixing the aqueous solution of lipase (1 mL) with the SILLP-6 (1 g, see Table 1). The mixture was gently shaken for 6 h at room temperature for enzyme adsorption. The supernatant was recovered, and the support washed with water to remove any non-adsorbed enzyme. The resulting immobilised CALB derivative (7.2 mg protein/g SILLP) was frozen at -20 °C, lyophilised and finally stored in a desiccator at 6 °C for further use.

Glycidyl (Meth)Acrylate Synthesis in [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] Catalysed by Lipase.

Into a 3-mL vial, vinyl acrylate or vinyl methacrylate (1.9 mmol), were mixed with glycidol (2.2 mmol). Then, the corresponding amount of [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] was added to reach a final concentration of 50 % (w/w) with respect to the overall mass. The resulting reaction mixture was pre-incubated for 10 minutes at 60 °C leading to a monophasic system. Finally, the reaction was started by adding the immobilized lipase (Novozym 435, Lypozyme TL IM or Lypozyme RM IM, 40 mg), or the CALB-SE (10 µL, 10.3 mg/mL). This mixture was shaken (300 rpm) for the desired time at 60 °C. For time course profiles, identical reaction vials were run simultaneously, and each point of the profile was obtained by analysing the full content of one of them. Thus, at the desired reaction time, the reaction medium of the selected vial was placed into a test tube coupled with a centrifugal nylon filter (0.2 µm pore size), cooled in a freezer (-20 °C) for 2 h, and finally centrifuged (15000 rpm, 10 min) at 0 °C. The centrifugation step led to a top SLIL/Novozym solid phase being retained by the filter, and a bottom liquid phase for the reaction product (see Figure 1). For each case, a 10 µL aliquot of the filtrated liquid fraction was taken and dissolved in 490 µL of acetone and directly analysed by gas chromatography.

Protocol for the Separation of GCA (or GCMA) from [C₁₆mim][NTf₂].

An aliquot (0.5 mL) of the reaction mixture, containing the GCA (or GCMA) and [C₁₆mim][NTf₂], was added to a 1 mL centrifugal vial coupled to a centrifugal nylon filter (0.2 µm pore size, see Fig. 1) at 60 °C. The system was cooled to -20 °C for 3 h to obtain a full solidification of the mixture, and then centrifuged (15000 rpm, 5 min) at -5 °C, leading to the filtration of the GCA (or GCMA) product, as a liquid phase, to the bottom of the tube, whereas the IL (solid phase) remained in the nylon filter. To improve the separation of the IL from the product fraction, the filtrate (0.25 mL) was processed by three consecutive cooling/centrifugation cycles through the centrifugal nylon filter.²⁵ For the determination of the residual IL content in product, an aliquot (20 mg) of the product liquid fraction was dissolved in acetone-δ₆ (0.48 mL) containing TFA (10 µL, internal standard) and analysed by 400 MHz ¹⁹F NMR in a Bruker AC 300E spectrometer.

SILLP-catalysed synthesis of GCA or GCMA by Cycloaddition of Carbon Dioxide.

A 3-mL open glass vial containing IL-free glycidyl (meth)acrylate (100 μ L) and the corresponding SILLPs (30 mg) was placed in a stainless-steel reactor system (250 mL volume, Berghof GmbH), equipped with mechanical stirring and temperature and pressure control. The reaction was carried out by pressurizing the system with CO₂ (0.1, 0.5 or 1 MPa) for the desired reaction time at 60 °C. At the end of the selected reaction time, the stainless-steel reactor was cooled in an ice bath for 15 min, and then slowly depressurized before opening. Finally, the reaction mixture contained in the glass-vial was collected and centrifuged, and the SILLP was separated and recovered, while the liquid product mixture used for GC analysis. To avoid sampling mistakes, the same reaction was simultaneously cloned in different vials for each selected reaction time. Thus, at the desired reaction time, each full reaction medium was used as the corresponding sample for analysis. For each case, a 10 μ L aliquot of the product liquid fraction was taken and dissolved in 490 μ L of acetone, and then directly analysed by gas chromatography.

One-Pot Synthesis of GCA or GCMA in Solvent-Free medium.

A 3-mL open glass vial containing vinyl acrylate, or vinyl methacrylate (1.9 mmol), glycidol (2.2 mmol) and CALB-SILLP-6 (60 mg,) was placed into a stainless-steel reactor (250 mL volume, Berghoff GmbH) equipped with mechanical stirring, and temperature and pressure control. The reaction was carried out by pressurizing the system with CO₂ (1 MPa) for 6 h at 60 °C. At the end of the reaction, the stainless-steel reactor was cooled into an ice bath for 15 min, and then slowly depressurized before opening. Finally, the reaction mixture contained into the glass-vial was centrifuged for CALB-SILLP-6 recovery, while the liquid product mixture was used for gas chromatography analysis.

Gas Chromatography Analysis.

Gas chromatography analysis was performed with a GC-2010-Plus apparatus (Shimadzu Europe, Germany) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a HP-5 column (50 m x 0.32 mm x 0.52 μ m, Teknokroma, Spain). Substrates and products were analysed under the following conditions: carrier gas (He) at 129.9 mL/min; injector temperature, 220 °C; split ratio 90:1; temperature program: 40 °C, 8 min; 13 °C/min, 300 °C, 2 min; detector temperature, 300 °C. Peak retention times (min) were as follows: glycidol, 9.8; vinyl acrylate, 8.1; vinyl methacrylate, 11.3; glycidyl acrylate, 16.6; glycidyl methacrylate, 18.0; GC, 20.5; GCA, 22.5; GCMA, 23.4.

Identification of products by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The GC-MS analyses were carried out by using a GC-6890 apparatus (Agilent, USA) coupled to a MS-5973 (Agilent, USA) system. The GC system was equipped with a HP-5MS column (30 x 0.25 μ m x 0.25 μ m, Agilent, USA) used under the following conditions: carrier gas (He) at 103 mL/min; inlet split ratio: 100:1; temperature program: 40 °C, 8 min; 13 °C/min, 300 °C, 2 min; MS source ionization energy 70 eV. The scan time was 0.5 s, covering a mass range 400-800 amu mass range. GCA, retention time (rt, min): 10.4, positive ion (m/z): 55.1, 100.0, 117.0, 173.0; GCMA, rt: 11.1, positive ion (m/z): 41.1, 69.1, 86.1, 102.0, 117.0, 186.1.

Figure 3. Time course profile for the Novozym 435-catalysed synthesis of glycidyl methacrylate (●), or glycidyl acrylate (■) by the transesterification of vinyl (meth)acrylate with glycidol by using a 1:1.2 (mol/mol, respectively) ratio in 50% w/w [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] at 60 °C.

Results and discussion

Lipase-catalysed Glycidyl (meth)acrylate ester synthesis.

Different immobilized lipases (Novozym 435, Lipozyme TL IM or Lipozyme RM IM) were evaluated as biocatalysts for the synthesis of glycidyl acrylate or glycidyl methacrylate by transesterification of several acyl donor esters (*i.e.* vinyl acrylate, vinyl methacrylate, or methyl methacrylate) with glycidol. The reaction was performed using the IL [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] as the reaction medium or, alternatively, under solvent-free conditions at 60 °C (see Table 1).

Fig. 3 depicts a representative example of the yield time-course profiles obtained for the synthesis of glycidyl acrylate and glycidyl methacrylate catalysed by Novozym 435 in [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] at 60 °C. As can be seen, a 100 % yield was obtained for both products, although the first one was obtained significantly faster than the second. These results demonstrated the excellent suitability of this biocatalyst/IL system for the preparation of both glycidyl acrylate and glycidyl methacrylate under mild conditions. Table 1 shows the influence of the use of different lipases derivatives and reaction media on these syntheses, as a function of the nature of the acyl donor. It should be noted that the reaction did not occur in the absence of the enzyme (Entry 1 and Entry 13, Table 1), or using the

non-immobilised CALB-SE as catalyst (Entry 12, Table 1). When vinyl methacrylate was used as the acyl donor (synthesis of glycidyl

IL as the reaction medium seems to be key for this biocatalytic transformation, as it has been reported that the same enzymatic reaction carried out in *t*-butanol reaches a 95% yield after 24 h.²⁰

Table 1. Results for the glycidyl (meth)acrylate synthesis catalysed by different lipases for the transesterification of several acyl donors with glycidol in [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] or in a solvent-free medium at 60 °C.

Entry	Enzyme ^a	Medium	Acyl Donor ^b	Yield (%) ^c
1	None	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VMA	0
2	TL IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VMA	37
3	TL IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MMA	0
4	TL IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MA	6
5	RM IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VMA	90
6	RM IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MMA	2
7	RM IM	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MA	12
8	Novozym 435	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VMA	100
9	Novozym 435	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VA	100
10	Novozym 435	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MMA	36
11	Novozym 435	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	MA	40
12	CALB-SE	[C ₁₆ mim][NTf ₂]	VMA	0
13	None	Solvent-free	VA	0
14	TL IM	Solvent-free	VA	12
15	TL IM	Solvent-free	MA	4
16	TL IM	Solvent-free	MMA	0
17	RM IM	Solvent-free	VA	22
18	RM IM	Solvent-free	MA	10
19	RM IM	Solvent-free	MMA	2
20	Novozym 435	Solvent-free	VA	97
21	Novozym 435	Solvent-free	VMA	46
22	Novozym 435	Solvent-free	MMA	0
23	Novozym 435	Solvent-free	MA	16

^aTL IM, Immobilized *Thermomyces lanuginosus* lipase (Lypozyme TL[®]); RM IM, Immobilized *Rhizomucor miehei* (Lypozyme RM[®]); Novozym 435[®], Immobilized *Candida antarctica* lipase B; CALB-SE, CALB aqueous solution; ^bAcyl donors: VMA, vinyl methacrylate; VA, vinyl acrylate; MMA, methyl methacrylate; MA, methyl acrylate; ^cDeviation errors < 2% in all instances; reaction time: 1 h (for VA); 5 h (for VMA and MMA).

methacrylate) in the IL reaction medium (see Entries 2, 5 and 8, Table 1), the best result was obtained using the commercial immobilized CALB derivative (Novozym 435, 100% product yield after 5 h). Other immobilized lipases led to lower yields, especially in the case of the lipase from *Thermomyces lanuginosus* (Lypozyme TL IM) with only *ca.* 37% yield. The result shown by Lypozyme TL IM was even worse when methyl ester substrates were used as the acyl donor (see Entries 3-4, Table 1), a behaviour also observed for the case of Lypozyme RM IM (see Entries 6-7, Table 1), and Novozym 435 (see Entries 10-11, Table 1). In all cases, Novozyme 435 was shown as a better biocatalyst than Lypozyme TL IM and Lypozyme RM IM to perform the synthesis of glycidyl (meth)acrylate. This better suitability Novozyme 435 was also observed when the same immobilized enzymes derivatives were used for the synthesis of cinnamyl propionate in SLILs.²⁵ Regarding the effect of the nature of the acyl donor used for the synthesis of glycidyl (meth)acrylate by means of the Novozym 435/[C₁₆mim][NTf₂] reaction system (Entries 8-11, Table 1), best results (100% product yield) were obtained when using acyl vinyl esters, as result of the tautomerization of the released vinyl alcohol to acetaldehyde that shifts reaction towards the desired outcome.¹⁹ Furthermore, the role of the [C₁₆mim][NTf₂]

Figure 4. Glycidyl methacrylate product yield obtained during continuous operation cycles for the Novozym 435-catalysed transesterification of vinyl methacrylate with glycidol in 50% (v/v) [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] (empty bars), or solvent-free system (filled bars), for 5 h reaction at 60 °C.

Alternatively, the proposed biocatalytic transformations in solvent-free systems were also studied (Entries 14-23, Table 1). As can be seen, Novozym 435 was again revealed as the best biocatalyst. Noteworthy, under solvent-free conditions, the yields obtained were always clearly lower than those obtained in IL-systems, highlighting the positive effect of ILs as reaction media. In solvent-free media, glycidol also acts as a hydrophilic solvent that may strip the essential water molecules interacting with enzymes, resulting in fast biocatalyst deactivation.^{22a} The protective effect of hydrophobic ILs, based on the [NTf₂] anion and 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium cation, have been related to the ability of these ILs to maintain the native structure of proteins even under harsh conditions,^{22c} as demonstrated by circular dichroism and fluorescence spectroscopy studies on the secondary structures of different proteins (*i.e.* α -chymotrypsin,^{32a} CALB,^{32b} etc.).

Figure 4 shows the glycidyl methacrylate yield obtained by consecutive cycles of recovery and reuse of Novozym 435 biocatalysts from IL-based and solvent-free reaction media. As can be seen, upon recycling the [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] system showed to be highly stable system in comparison with the reaction under solvent-free conditions, providing an excellent activity (99% yield) for six reaction cycles. Thus, the use of ILs offers significant advantages as reaction media for the immobilized enzyme, highlighting again its

suitability with respect to solvent-free system for further scaling up processes.²³

The higher biocatalytic efficiency in IL systems as reaction media is likely to be attributed to the over-stabilization effects of ILs on

Table 2. Influence of the nature of the SILLPs in the synthesis of GCMA obtained by cycloaddition of carbon dioxide (0.2 MPa) to glycidyl methacrylate (6h, 60 °C).

Entry	SILLP ^a	Cation	Anion	ILs loading (meq. IL/supp) ^b	Yield (%)
1	SILLP-1	[1-Methylimidazolium]	[Cl]	1.01	52
2	SILLP-2	[1-Methylimidazolium]	[Cl]	3.18	74
3	SILLP-3	[1-Butylimidazolium]	[Cl]	2.80	100
4	SILLP-4	[1-Butylimidazolium]	[NTf ₂] ^c	1.46	4
5	SILLP-5	[1-Decyl-2-methylimidazolium]	[Cl]	0.88	44
6	SILLP-6	[1-Decyl-2-methylimidazolium]	[Cl]	2.20	100

^a Prepared from a 4.3 meq Cl/g, gel-type (microporous) polymers, 1% DVB, as reported in reference [30]. ^b Imidazolium unit loading calculated by elemental analysis. ^c [NTf₂]: Bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide.

enzymes, providing an excellent microenvironment for such biocatalysts.²² For the case of solvent-free systems, substrates act as non-aqueous organic solvents in direct interaction with the enzyme, which can facilitate the deactivation by the stripping of the essential water-shell around the protein.²³

At the view of these results, the Novozym 435/[C₁₆mim][NTf₂] system was selected as the reaction medium for the synthesis of glycidyl acrylate and glycidyl methacrylate by using vinyl esters as acyl donors. Hydrophobic ILs based on cations with long alkyl side-chains, like [C₁₆mim][NTf₂], are temperature switchable ionic liquid/solid phases that behave as sponge-like systems (Sponge-Like Ionic Liquids, SLILs).²³ These ILs show the ability “to soak up” hydrophobic compounds (*i.e.* geranyl acetate,²³ methyl oleate,²⁴ benzyl propionate,²⁵ etc.) as a liquid phase, becoming solid phases after cooling, and then to “wrung out” these compounds by centrifugation protocols. Thus, they are suitable reaction media to integrate the biocatalytic synthesis and direct product/catalysts separation, enabling a simple and efficient recycling of the active biocatalyst/SLIL phases. Accordingly, a straightforward approach for glycidyl (meth)acrylate separation and recovery of the SLIL was achieved by the cooling (-20 °C) of the reaction mixture, and its subsequent centrifugation (-10 °C, 15,000 rpm) through nylon filtration membranes (0.2 μm pore size, see Figure 1). After the application of three consecutive cooling/centrifugation steps, a 2.5 % (w/w) residual IL was detected in the filtrate glycidyl product fraction, as determined by ¹⁹F NMR analysis.

SILLPs-catalysed synthesis of GCA or GCMA by cycloaddition of carbon dioxide to glycidyl (meth)acrylate.

The preparation of cyclic carbonates through the catalytic cycloaddition of carbon dioxide to epoxides, following simple and harmless reaction protocols, is of great interest because of the added benefit from CO₂ utilization as a carbon resource.^{6,12} Covalently supported ionic liquid-like phases (SILLPs) obtained by functionalization of polymer surfaces with IL-like units provide

systems having the main features of bare ILs (e.g. stability, tunable polarity, nanostructure, etc.).³³

Besides, the crosslinked polymeric backbone offers an additional design vector to optimize their macroscopic and process properties.³⁴ They provide similar features than bulk ILs but simplify

Figure 5. Time-course profile for the [1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium][Cl]-based SILLP-catalysed synthesis of GCMA by the cycloaddition of CO₂ to glycidyl methacrylate, as a function of CO₂ pressure (●, 0.1 MPa; ○, 0.2 MPa; △, 0.5 MPa; □, 1 MPa) at 60 °C.

product isolation, eliminate (eco)toxicological concerns, greatly reduce the amount of ILs and facilitate their full recovery/reuse in continuous green chemical processes.²⁷ In a similar way to liquid IL-phases, SILLPs can be also used to fine-tune the catalyst performance assisting the activation of the catalyst, generating novel catalytic species, improving catalyst stability, and influencing the selectivity.³⁵ SILLPs based on alkylimidazolium moieties covalently attached to styrene-divinyl benzene supports (see Table 2) can be potential catalysts for the synthesis of the corresponding cyclic carbonates from previously obtained glycidyl methacrylate glycidyl acrylate (see Fig. 1). The initial SILLPs tested were based on gel-type polymers, as these SILLPs have been reported to swell well in some epoxides, providing good accessibility of the functional sites and, accordingly, potential reactivity.^{30c} Thus, the evaluation of different SILLPs for the cycloaddition of CO₂ was carried out under solvent-free conditions at 0.2 MPa of CO₂ and 60 °C.

The nucleophilicity of the counter anion was a key factor to obtain catalytic active SILLPs. All the SILLPs bearing chloride anion as the counterion were catalytically active systems, while essentially no activity was obtained when the [NTf₂] was assayed as the anion (entries 3 vs 4, Table 2). It must be also mentioned that, under the same experimental conditions, the unfunctionalized PS-DVB polymer was not catalytically active towards cyclic carbonate formation. The increase in the IL loading in the polymeric matrix led to higher

catalytic efficiencies for GCMA synthesis when the same alkylimidazolium cation was used, (Entries 1 vs 2 and 5 vs 6, Table 2). Regarding the effect of the alkyl chain length of the imidazolium moiety, ca. 100% GCMA yields were achieved for 1-butylimidazolium and 1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium cations (see entries 3 and 6, Table 2), while a slightly lower yield (74 %, entry 2, Table 2) was observed for 1-methylimidazolium.

Zang *et al.* observed the excellent suitability of [1-aminopropyl-3-methylimidazolium][Cl] as a catalyst for the synthesis of propylene carbonate from propylene oxide, obtaining up to 96% yield after 4 h reaction at 1 MPa and at 120 °C.³⁶ Also, Dyson *et al.* reported the suitability of imidazolium ionic liquids, based on several halide counter anions (*i.e.* [Cl], [Br] and [I]) and with different acidic protons in the imidazolium cation, to catalyse the conversion of epichlorohydrin into 3-chloropropylene carbonate.³⁷ This study concluded that the interaction between the imidazolium cation and halide anion, and thus the overall nucleophilicity of the halide anion, also affects the reaction mechanism of cyclic carbonate formation. Fig. 5 depicts the time-course profiles of GCMA synthesis catalysed by SILLP-6 as a function of CO₂ pressure at 60 °C. As can be seen, this supported IL-catalyst provided full conversion of the epoxide substrate into the corresponding carbonate for all the assayed CO₂ pressures after 20 h reaction. A similar suitability of the SILLP-6 catalyst was observed for glycidyl acrylate, a full transformation to GCA being obtained after 20 h at 60 °C. For CO₂ pressures higher than 0.2 MPa, cyclic carbonate yields > 95% could be achieved in only 6 h. Only for the case of 0.1 MPa CO₂ pressure, a slightly lower yield (85%) was obtained for this reaction time. The results achieved with the studied SILLPs for the synthesis of GCMA are in good agreement with those reported when using either homogeneous or heterogeneous organocatalytic systems.^{10,21} High CO₂ pressure could enhance the absorption of CO₂ in the solution of glycidyl (meth)acrylate, and thus enable the reaction equilibrium to shift towards carbonate formation. However, it should be taken into account that as a consequence of the high CO₂ sorption capacity of imidazolium-based ILs, a positive partition effect on CO₂ concentration might occur in the microenvironment of SILLPs particles, resulting in no significant changes in activity when pressure was higher than 0.2 MPa.³⁸ It is worth mentioning, however, that for other reported systems high temperatures (90-100 °C) and pressures ranging from 1.0-3.0 MPa are required to achieve the same catalytic efficiency. This demonstrates the excellent suitability of the alkylimidazolium moiety as a simple, cheap, and easy to be prepared catalyst for the solvent-free synthesis of GCMA by the direct cycloaddition of CO₂ with glycidyl methacrylate. Thus, for instance, the synthesis of propylene carbonate by the cycloaddition of CO₂ to propylene oxide using a Lewis basic IL as catalyst has been studied as a function of CO₂ pressure (ranged from 0.5 to 7 MPa) at 140 °C. Full conversion was at short reaction times was only obtained for pressures higher than 1 MPa, being also pointed that maximum yield could be attained at 0.5 MPa by prolonging reaction time. Besides, CO₂ pressures over 9 MPa produced a decay in product yield, being associated to a retard in the interaction between epoxide and the catalyst, which led to selecting 1 MPa as a suitable CO₂ pressure.³⁹ The use of lower CO₂ pressures has the additional advantage of reducing the hazards associated to the work under pressure.

The strategy here developed allows the synthesis of acrylic carbonates by the integration of these two consecutive catalytic steps under mild conditions (60 °C) (Fig. 1). In the first step, the selective transesterification of vinyl (meth)acrylate with glycidol catalysed by an immobilized CALB produced the corresponding glycidyl (meth)acrylate with a high yield, where the excellent

Figure 6. One-pot chemo-enzymatic synthesis of GCA or GCMA (**3**) by means of two consecutive reactions carried out by immobilized CALB onto 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium-based SILLPs, as a dual catalyst, under solvent-free conditions. Vinyl (meth)acrylate (**1**); glycidol (**2**). Vinyl acrylate (R = -H); vinyl methacrylate (R = -CH₃)

suitability of the [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] as the reaction medium is doubtless when compared with solvent-free media (see Table I).

Although this glycidyl (meth)acrylate intermediate can easily be separated from the [C₁₆mim][NTf₂] SILI for the further carbonate formation under solvent-free conditions, its residual IL content seems to tarnish the overall greenness of the process. Additional purification steps of the glycidyl (meth)acrylate fraction could be developed for the proposed approach, but a more appropriate alternative can be the development of an improved protocol for easily producing pure acrylic carbonates as described in the next section.

One-pot chemo-enzymatic synthesis of GCMA under solvent-free conditions.

To improve the efficiency of the process, a multifunctional catalytic system was designed for the one-pot chemo-enzymatic synthesis of GCMA. It has been reported that SILLPs show, at the molecular level, the same fundamental properties of the bulk ILs as suitable microenvironments for enzyme catalysis. Thus, the immobilization by simple adsorption of CALB onto SILLPs bearing 1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium cations has been reported as an excellent biocatalytic system for continuous flow processes in sCO₂, such as the synthesis of citronellol esters by transesterification of vinyl alkyl esters with citronellol,^{28a} and the synthesis of biodiesel by transesterification of vegetable oil with methanol.^{28b} The specific nature of the SILLP allows to fine-tune the biocatalytic efficiency in terms of activity and stability through the appropriate selection of parameters such as the resin morphology and the loading and nature

of the IL-like groups (cation and anion). Besides, the presence of the IL-like units also contributes to the long-term stability of the corresponding supported biocatalyst, which allows their prolonged use even under microwave irradiation, allowing continuous flow processes in scCO_2 .²⁷

Figure 7. Operational stability of CALB immobilized in the SILLP bearing [1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium][Cl] moieties (SILLP-6, 30 mg) for the production of GCMA by means of two consecutive reactions in a one-pot system, using vinyl methacrylate (1.9 mmol), glycidol (2.2 mmol), and CO_2 (1 MPa) as substrates, after 6 h at 60 °C.

In this context, the incorporation of CALB onto a supported ionic liquid such as SILLP-6 by simple adsorption should generate a multicatalytic chemo-enzymatic material able to carry out, in a one-pot system, the two catalytic steps required for the synthesis of GCMA from a mixture of vinyl methacrylate, glycidol and CO_2 (Fig. 6). To our delight, this CALB-SILLP-6 derivative under solvent-free conditions provided 100% yield of the desired GCA after pressurizing a mixture of vinyl methacrylate, glycidol and CO_2 at 1 MPa for 6 h at 60 °C. This result demonstrates the excellent suitability of the covalently attached IL as an appropriate microenvironment for the enzyme catalysis in solvent-free conditions. It should be noted that Novozym 435 was only able to produce a 47 % glycidyl acrylate yield under solvent-free conditions (see Entry 13, Table 1), while 100% glycidyl acrylate yield was obtained in homogenous IL phase (see Entry 6, Table 1). Furthermore, the final pure GCA product was easily obtained by simple filtration of the CALB-SILLP-6 opening the way for a simple recycling of the catalytic system in multiple consecutive cycles. Figure 7 shows the operational stability profile for the one-pot synthesis of GCMA catalysed by CALB-SILLP-6 under solvent-free conditions at 60 °C. As can be seen, GCMA yields were essentially quantitative (100%) and remained practically unchanged after 5 consecutive cycles of reuse. However, without the presence of IL the deactivation of the enzyme occurred upon reuse (Figure 4). The microenvironment provided to the CALB by the IL-like units present in the SILLP contributes, in a similar way to that the observed in the case of bulk ILs, to maintain the catalytic performance of the enzyme, hampering its deactivation.^{26,27}

The covalent functionalization of solid surfaces with IL-like moieties not only provides a practical solution for avoiding the lixiviation of the IL phase during processing,^{22c} in addition, SILLPs lead to amazing

synergies when combined with enzymes because of the unique ILs properties for improving the catalytic efficiency (e.g. improved activity and enhanced stability, etc.), and also allow the design of smart approaches for product separation (e.g. flow biocatalytic reactor in scCO_2).²⁸ These results demonstrated that the SILLPs can reproduce the behaviour observed for biocatalytic processes in bulk ILs, using significant less amount of IL equivalents, leading to more active and stable catalysts and, at the same time, enabling a simple and pure product isolation, and catalyst reuse.

Conclusions

A new chemo-enzymatic approach for the synthesis of GCA or GCMA from vinyl acrylate (or vinyl methacrylate), glycidol and CO_2 was successfully carried out in SLILs and solvent-free reaction media. The strategy was based on two consecutive catalytic steps, involving the selective transesterification of vinyl (meth)acrylate with glycidol by immobilized CALB (*i.e.* commercial Novozym 435, or CALB adsorbed onto SILLPs) to produce glycidyl (meth)acrylate. This initial step is, followed by the cycloaddition of CO_2 to the resulting epoxy moiety catalysed by a SILLP containing covalently attached 1-alkyl-2-methylimidazolium moieties (see Figure 1). The SLIL $[\text{C}_{16}\text{mim}][\text{NTf}_2]$ was shown to be an excellent reaction medium for the lipase-catalysed transesterification reaction, which was also demonstrated by the great operational stability observed, although a residual IL content was observed in the extracted product fraction. In the same way, an appropriate selection of the structure of the SILLP used as the catalyst, including its morphology and the nature of the cation and the anion, as well as the CO_2 pressure have been shown to be key parameters to achieve the full conversion of the epoxide ring to the cyclic carbonate in solvent-free systems.

When using the CALB-SILLP system as the catalyst, an efficient and clean protocol for the one-pot chemo-enzymatic synthesis of GCMA under solvent-free conditions was successfully achieved. By this alternative approach, the same catalyst particles carried out consecutively both the enzymatic and the chemical catalytic steps under mild conditions, allowing a full recovery and reuse of all the elements of the reaction system, as well as the easy separation of nearly pure product, pointing out this one-pot approach in solvent-free as more appropriate. The excellent suitability of the CALB immobilized onto a SILLPs bearing [1-decyl-2-methylimidazolium][Cl] was demonstrated by the maintenance of the two different catalytic activities involved in this process for many operation cycles. By using this approach, almost pure GCMA was obtained under mild conditions (*i.e.* 60 °C, 0.2-1 MPa CO_2 pressure).

These results clearly show how the combination of both ILs and (bio)catalyst technologies has opened a new sustainable way to contribute to the reduction of the CO_2 concentration in the atmosphere through its capture and incorporation into added-value products of interest for the synthesis of bio-based polymers.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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